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LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANISATIONS ON INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS (IDPs) CAMPS IN ABUJA-NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examines impact of international non-governmental organisation, who on internally displaced persons camps in Abuja. The basic contention of this resource work is to analyse the challenges confronting NGOs on the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camp in Abuja. The challenges encountered by Nigeria state in managing the plights of IPDs was the absence of legal institutional framework responsible for proving short, medium and long term measure for their plights, provision of assistance, protection, reintegration and resettlement for IDPs is mostly undertaken by non-governmental organisation NGOs and also others agencies of government on ad-hoc and reactive basis. The IDPs management agencies get fund mainly through revenue international aids and donations. The funds they get are more often not sufficient to meet the increasing needs of IDPs in Abuja. However, the study employed both primary and secondary method of data collection. For the primary data questionnaire were administered to various selected organisations and interview was conducted. While for the secondary data method quantitative data were collected, State Fragility Theory was adopted as a theoretical underpinning. The study concluded that inspite all the government effort to alleviate the IDPs crisis in Abuja, there seems to be obvious inadequate of effective programme services delivery of government in tackling the problem of IDPs camps in Abuja. The study therefore recommends that International NGOs should move beyond short-term relief to design and implement sustainable livelihood programmes, including vocational training, small business grants, and agricultural empowerment schemes for IDPs. Such programmes would promote self-reliance and reduce dependency on aid. The Nigerian government, through the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), should develop a comprehensive national policy framework that clearly defines roles, responsibilities, and coordination mechanisms between government agencies and humanitarian actors.

Keywords: Non-Governmental Organizations, Conflict, Security

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INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of internal displacement has become a major humanitarian and developmental concern in contemporary global politics. According to the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC, 2023), over 71.1 million people were internally displaced worldwide due to conflict, violence, and disasters. Africa alone accounts for more than one-third of this figure, with Nigeria among the most affected countries. Internal displacement in Nigeria is primarily driven by armed conflict, communal clashes, terrorism, and natural disasters (Adewale, 2022). These challenges have generated large populations of internally displaced persons (IDPs) who require humanitarian support, protection, and long-term reintegration assistance. Nigeria's internal displacement crisis gained intensity after 2009 with the escalation of Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, and farmer-herder conflicts. According to Olanrewaju, Omotoso, and Alabi (2018), more than 3 million Nigerians have been displaced within the country over the last decade, with concentration in the North-East and North-Central regions. Although Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), is not at the epicentre of the insurgency, it hosts several IDP camps and informal settlements that accommodate displaced persons from Borno, Adamawa, Yobe, Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa States (Onah, 2020). The presence of these camps, such as New Kuchingoro, Durumi, and Area One, underscores Abuja's role as a humanitarian hub for displaced populations seeking safety and better living conditions (Oluwaseun & Eboh, 2021).

However, the living conditions of IDPs in Abuja camps remain deplorable. Studies reveal that most IDPs in the FCT experience poor shelter, food insecurity, limited access to education, inadequate health facilities, and lack of potable water and sanitation services (Owoaje, Uchendu & Ajayi, 2016). These humanitarian gaps necessitated the intervention of International Non-Governmental Organisations (INGOs) whose mandates are centered on humanitarian relief, advocacy, and developmental assistance. According to Krause (2014), INGOs play a crucial role in filling the institutional and logistical vacuum often left by weak state responses in crisis situations.

Since 2015, various INGOs such as Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), the International Rescue Committee (IRC), the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), the Red Cross, and Save the Children have provided humanitarian aid in IDP camps within and around Abuja. Their interventions include healthcare delivery, food distribution, education in emergencies, psychosocial support, and protection of vulnerable groups (International Rescue Committee, 2021). These organisations often collaborate with the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), and local NGOs to enhance coordination and service delivery (Eze, 2020). INGOs' activities significantly improve the welfare and resilience of displaced populations. Adesoji and Onifade (2019) found that INGO-led humanitarian assistance improved food security and access to healthcare among IDPs in Abuja and Nasarawa State. Similarly, Adewale (2022) emphasized that INGOs contribute to reducing human suffering and restoring dignity to displaced persons through advocacy and protection programmes.

Statement of the Problem

The phenomenon of internal displacement in Nigeria has escalated over the past decade as a result of violent conflicts, insurgency, communal clashes, and natural disasters. Since 2009, the Boko Haram insurgency and its attendant security challenges have displaced millions of Nigerians across various states. By 2024, estimates from the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC, 2024) indicated that more than 3.6 million persons were internally displaced across Nigeria, with a significant number migrating to the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, in search of safety, stability, and basic amenities. Despite being a political and administrative centre, Abuja hosts several IDP settlements such as New

Kuchingoro, Durumi, Wassa, and Kuje camps, where displaced persons live under harsh conditions with limited access to health care, food, shelter, education, and protection services (Olanrewaju, Omotoso & Alabi, 2018).

In response to the humanitarian crisis, numerous International Non-Governmental Organisations (INGOs) have been actively involved in providing relief and developmental support to IDPs in Abuja. Organisations such as the International Rescue Committee (IRC), Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF), Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), Save the Children, and the Red Cross have implemented programmes in areas including food security, health, water and sanitation, education, and psychosocial support (Eze, 2020). These interventions are designed to alleviate the suffering of displaced persons, promote dignity, and facilitate reintegration and resilience. However, despite the large presence and activities of INGOs in IDP camps, the living conditions of displaced persons remain largely deplorable, with recurrent reports of hunger, inadequate housing, child malnutrition, poor hygiene, sexual abuse, and limited livelihood opportunities.

INGOs' humanitarian efforts have not yielded proportionate and sustainable impacts in Abuja's IDP camps due to a range of challenges. These include poor coordination with government agencies, inadequate funding, overlapping mandates, weak monitoring and evaluation systems, and dependence on donor priorities that may not always align with local realities (Adewale, 2022; Onah, 2020). Furthermore, gaps in policy implementation and inconsistent government support undermine the long-term developmental impact of these humanitarian efforts. Another critical issue is the urban context of displacement in Abuja, which presents unique challenges distinct from traditional rural camps. Many IDPs in the FCT reside in informal settlements rather than formal camps, making data collection, needs assessment, and aid delivery difficult (Oluwaseun & Eboh, 2021). Therefore, despite the presence of multiple INGOs and the considerable resources devoted to humanitarian assistance, there remains a critical gap between humanitarian input and tangible improvement in IDP welfare and durable solutions.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to assess the impact of international non-Governmental organization on internally displaced persons camps in Abuja, Nigeria. Other specific objectives of the study included:

- i. To examine the impact of International Non-Governmental Organisation (NGOs) in tackling economic hardship and social problem of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps in Abuja.
- ii. To establish the impacts of Non-Governmental Organisation (NGOs) on women and children in Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps in Abuja.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Non-Governmental Organizations

The term "nongovernmental organization" generally refers to organizations that are; (i) not government based; and (ii) not profit oriented. These organizations, however, vary in themselves. In some developed nations like the United States, for instance, Non-Governmental organizations may be referred to as "private voluntary organizations," while in developing countries like in most African nations, NGOs may be referred to as "voluntary development organizations or civil society organizations. The diversity of NGOs strains any simple definition. They include many groups and institutions that are entirely or largely independent of government and that have primarily humanitarian or cooperative rather than commercial objectives. They are private organizations in developed nations who render international development support; they may also be local or indigenous groups who are

regionally or nationally organized; or a small group of people in villages. Many independent humanitarian support-providing groups fall under the broad heading of NGOs. They include; religious organizations and charities that raise funds for the support and development of those in dire need, provide basic social support services and amenities including food, clean water, clothing, and shelter among others and promote community organization. Non-Governmental organizations also include community associations, workers/independent cooperatives, social/friendship/professional clubs and societies, women's groups and religious associations.

NGOs fall under the broad category of "Civil Society Organizations" (an umbrella term that includes; non-governmental organizations (NGOs), charities, trusts, foundations, advocacy groups, and national and internal non-state associations (Wallace & Lewis, 2020; Ikelegbe, 2023). According to the World Bank (2020), civil societies are "a broad category of Nongovernmental and no-for-profit organizations that express the interests, concerns, and values of their members or individuals who are in need, on the basis of certain cultural, religious, political, ethical, religious, humanitarian or philanthropic grounds. As such Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) consist of humanitarian organizations such as; community associations, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), labour unions, social/professional clubs, local/community development associations, charities, religious organizations, as well as foundations" (World Bank 2020).

Diamond (2017) defines civil society as the realm of organized social life that is open, voluntary, self-generating, at least partially self-supporting, and autonomous from the state, and bound by a legal order or set of shared rules. It differs from the general society in that it involves a group of individuals with a common humanitarian aims who act collectively to express their concerns, passions, interest, preferences, and ideas, to achieve collective goals, to inform and/or bring pressing concerns about a group to the notice of the government, make demands on their behalf, contribute to the community and sustainable development of the state by providing social services, etc. Civil society, therefore, serves as that link between the state and the private sphere. In Diamond's view, civil society is an intermediary phenomenon, standing between the private sphere and the state. Thus, it excludes individual and family life, inward-looking group activity (for example, for recreation, entertainment, religious worship or spirituality), and the profit making enterprise of individual business firms.

Conflict

Conflict is an existing state of disagreement or hostility between two or more people (Nicholson, 2022). By this, it means two or more parties do not have an accord and are as such on two different parallels on the same issue. It thus suggests the pursuit of incompatible goals. Put differently, conflict means collision course; it also refers to opposition to existing view, stand, or position. In politics, conflict is more explicitly defined. Conflict is said to exist when two or more groups engage in a struggle over values and claims to status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure or eliminate the rivals (Jeong, 2020). Conflict is a demonstration of cross-purposes of distinct or similar political groups which often ends in political violence, and political violence, when contextualized in the Weberian sense, according to Anifowose, in his *Violence and Politics in Nigeria* (2022), is an acceptable weapon to ventilate anger. Goal incompatibility implies opposing or diametrically opposed motives or pursuits. For instance, the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics were pursuing incompatible goals (capitalist democracy and socialism respectively) between 1945 and 1990, an era historically referred to as the Cold War. The 'war' implies the conflict of ideologies and irreconcilability of foreign policies. The period between 1967 and 1970 witnessed the total breakdown of relations and concord in Nigeria, as the East seceded from the federation because of irreconcilable differences with the rest of Nigeria. This led to the Civil War, which further

aggravated the conflict because the East pursued the cause of sovereignty and nationhood, which ran contrary to the cause of 'unity' that the Nigerian government pursued.

Conflict also connotes different perceptions, which may not necessarily result in hostility. This way, conflict simply means 'a different perception' or view to an issue or situation (Barash and Webel, 2022). Here, it may mean a different interpretation of a motive, or a different world-view. These include religion, customs, cosmologies or values. Such differences may never culminate in direct and sharp confrontations. On the other hand, however, different perceptions, values or world-views may transcend just 'differences' and result in the extreme connotation of conflict. Inter-faith violence is a critical example of such breakdown. Sometime ago in Nigeria, a splinter group of the Oodua People's Congress (OPC) in the Southwest emerged as a result of growing differences in perceptions, motives interests and values. But soon after, the split and differences led to direct clashes and breakdown of law and order. Conflict may also connote hostility or physical confrontation (Jeong, 2020). When goal incompatibility or perception/value differences reach a crescendo, a manifestation of actual hostility or clashes is possible. In general literature, conflict is interchangeably used with other terms. This is where it becomes pertinent to mention words or terms that represent synonyms of conflict. These include contrast, disharmony, discord, struggle, contest, strife, antagonism, controversy, clash, rivalry, contest, contention, brawl, fisticuff, fight, battle, feud, combat and war. In politics, it is not too dissimilar; however, conflict technically means an existing state of disconnect between two or more parties on a prevailing issue.

Security

Security is a concept that is prior to the state and the state exists to promote that concept (Olabanji and Ese, 2024). Security is the prime responsibility of the state (Hobbes, 2016). The constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria clearly states that "the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary concern of the government" (FRN, 2019). It is not an exaggeration to state that the constitutional responsibility of Nigerian government to provide security for her subjects has in one way or the other failed due to the inability of government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives and properties and even that of economic activities.

The alarming rate of insecurity in northern Nigeria has increased; the crime rate and terrorist attacks in different parts of the country people living in the north is an unpalatable situation rendering them homeless (Abdurrahman and Zuwaira, 2016) In order to reduce the crime rate, the federal government has passed the antiterrorism act in 2011, installation of computer based Closed Circuit Television Cameras (CCTV), in some parts of the country, enhancement of surveillance as well as investigation of criminal related offences, heightening of physical security measures around the country aimed at deterring potential attacks, strengthening of the security agencies through provision of security facilities and the development of broadcast of security tips in mass media (Azazi, 2021).

The term security according to Akin (2008) is the situation that exists as a result of establishment of measures for the protection of persons, information and property against hostile persons' influences and nations. It is the existence of condition within which people of the society can go about their normal activities without any threat to their lives and properties. Igbuzor (2011), it demands safety from chronic threats and protection from harmful disruption

Impact of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in Tackling Economic and Social Problems in IDPs Camps

Non-governmental organizations and Civil society organizations in the views of Ikelegbe (2013) and Keane (1989) have globally become active non-state agents of

development saddled with the multifaceted responsibilities of providing social welfare, economic empowerment, humanitarian services, political participation, human capital development and economic activities. It is known as the third sector because it serves as a vibrant social intermediary between the state, business, and family (Harbeson, 1993). NGOs appear to play important role in social, political and economic development activities (Omede & Bakare, 2014). Therefore, vibrant Non-governmental organizations are the sine qua non to the sustenance of any nation's development. NGOs in the view of Gyimah-Boadi (2004) have contributed immensely to democratic consolidation and sustainable development in Nigeria. In fact, the responsibility of ensuring sustainable infrastructural development rest on the shoulder of NGOs. This is because; they are the agents of development in any nation. This is since the collaboration and participation of the NGOs is a crucial to successful implementation of development initiatives (Omede & Bakare, 2014). This agrees with the view of Ikelegbe (2013) that NGOs provides the oil that lubricates the relationship between the government, business outfits, and the people.

Non-Governmental organizations in Nigeria have since 1999 tried to advocate for the delivery of certain basic dividends of democracy to the citizens. They have also helped in the provision of basic economic and social services to Nigerians in both urban and rural areas. They provide soft loans and agricultural incentives to members of the public, provide employment opportunities and basic social amenities like schools, clinics, pipe borne water and other essential services (Shedrack 2015, Mercy 2012).

Many IDPs have little or no access to shelter, sanitation, clean water, education and good health care. This is because almost 60 percent of health infrastructure affected has been destroyed or damaged. To ameliorate the situation, the European Commission has supported the State with €143 million for the recovery and reconstruction needs of the people. The financing package brings EU's total support for the crisis in Borno State to €224.5 million for 2017 (European Union, 2017) while the World Bank (2016) is considering a \$2.1 billion loan to rebuild infrastructure in the Northeast and Borno State in particular.

Impact of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) on Human Security in IDPs Camp

In Nigeria, the post-election violence of 2011 saw about 65,000 persons internally displaced in the Northern part of the country (Osagioduwa & Oluwakorede, 2016). An estimation by the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) reports that from July to October, 2012, a total of 2.1 million residents were sacked by flood in Nigeria. Between January, 2013 and February, 2014, about 470,565 and 143,164 persons were displaced in Nigeria by internal conflicts and natural disasters, respectively, while internal displacement cuts across 24 states of the federation (Osagioduwa & Oluwakorede, 2016).

Reports have shown that a good number of persons are displaced as results of both federal and state governments' activities such as demolitions, the oil explorations in the Niger-Delta region leading to environmental degradation and pollution, loss of the people's sources of livelihood in the region. Under the Governor Fashola's led administration, over 1 million people were displaced from the demolition of Ijora, Oshodi, Makoko and many other communities (Hamzat, 2013). Although the causes of displacement differ, armed conflict and other forms of mass violence are the major causes of human displacement in the country. Since 2009 however, continuous and recurrent violence caused by Boko Haram insurgency in the Northern region of the country has resulted in the rapid increase of the number of internally displaced persons in the region. The Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC) recorded over 1 million internally displaced persons as of April 2015. However, the number of internally displaced persons as at December 2015 increased to over 2 million IDPs in the region. This is evident due to the Boko Haram insurgency which is identified as the

major cause of the internal displacement of people in the region with a percentage of 91.98% (Alobo & Obaji, 2016).

Moreover, just like the number of recorded internally displaced persons in the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) increased from 390,000 at December 2014 to more than 2 million at December, 2015 (Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs [OCHA], 2015). Northern Nigeria is a region of the country which has some of the least human indexes in the country. "71.5% of the population resides in abject poverty; over half of the residents are mal-nourished; about 85% are illiterate; and 60% are formally unemployed" (Abdulazeez, 2016). This explains the attractiveness of the Boko Haram sect in the region. The group recorded chains of attacks in various forms against local and international actors therefore leading to the displacement of over 2 million people across northern Nigeria (Oyewole, 2016). One of the consequences of this movement's violence is the displacement of people from their habitual homes as a result of fear over their lives. The Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC), recorded as at 2013, 3.3 million displaced persons in Nigeria especially as a result of the insurgency. It also recorded over 1 million internally displaced persons as of April 2015 and at December 2015, the total figure of IDPs identified in Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe amounted to 2,152,000 people (Alobo & Obaji, 2016). From the total figure of internally displaced persons in this region, the examination shows that "13.33 per cent were displaced due to communal clashes, 0.99 per cent by natural disasters and 85.68 per cent as a result of insurgency attacks by Boko Haram' activities in the region" (Obikaeze & Onuoha, 2016).

The Nigerian constitution places the responsibility of the welfare and the security of the general public on the government (Adamu & Rasheed, 2016). However, the Nigerian government has over the years failed in discharging the constitutional responsibilities that expects them to provide a secured and safe environment for both lives and properties of her citizens, which has caused insecurity in some states hence leading to human displacement for the fear of their lives. In a bid to curb the IDP crisis in Nigeria, the federal government of Nigeria, along with other African states became a signatory to the African Union Convention for the Protection of Internally Displaced Persons also known as the Kampala Convention of 2009. The Convention reflects the international guidance provided in the Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement as an international standard setting norm on IDPs (Ekpa & Dahlan, 2016). The main objective of the Kampala Convention is to "promote and strengthen regional and national measures to prevent or mitigate, prohibit and eliminate root causes of internal displacement as well as provide for durable solutions" (as cited in Kampala Convention, 2009). The establishment of National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) by the federal government was a bid to address and respond swiftly to emergency situations in the country. The Nigerian government has made several unending efforts to addressing the plights of IDPs by putting in place different strategies to address the IDPs crisis, paradoxically, the problems of hunger, overcrowding, poor sanitation, joblessness and insecurity continues to persist among internally displaced persons across the country (Itumo & Nwefuru, 2016). Moreover, there are IDPs camps set up in over 200 local government areas of Nigeria. These camps are provided in collaboration with the United Nations, other international organizations, and non-profit organizations (UNHCR, 2014). The Nigerian government also established programs to help alleviate the IDP crisis in the region such as the North-East Development Commission (NEDC), Presidential Committee on North East Initiative (PCNI). These efforts seem to have yielded little or no impact as crisis of internally displaced persons persists in the country.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted for the study is State Fragility Theory. The UK Department for the Development (United Kingdom, 2005) sees state fragility theory from the

humanitarian point of view, where the government cannot or will not deliver core functions to the majority of its people including the poor. He further sees a fragile state as the insecurity of the ruling elites which leads to the victimization of some or all of a nation's citizens as experienced by the Taliban's in Afghanistan. The state fragility theory stresses the fundamental failure of a state to perform functions necessary to meet citizen's basic needs and expectations. It also shows the incapability of government in assuring basic security, maintaining rule of law and justice, or providing basic services and economic opportunities for their citizens. The centrality of state fragility theory posits weak and ineffective central government with little practical control over much of its territory; non-provision of public services widespread corruption and criminality; refugees and involuntary movement of populations (OECD, 2008).

Rotberg (2003) notes that in a fragile state, there is a tendency for increase criminal violence which further weakens the state's authority. He further notes that fragile states are usually associated with tensed, deeply conflicted and dangerous warring factions which most times leads to breakdown of law and order, increased humanitarian disaster, which concerns not only the people directly affected, but also others in the country as well as people in neighboring states. As Gros (1996) notes, ethnic genocide in Rwanda and the Balkans or flight of Haitians to Florida can hardly be ignored by the international community. Torres and Anderson (2004) argue that conflicts, humanitarian crises, human right violations, constitute to the global and local impact of fragile states. Collier et al. (2003) identify three ripple effects that emerge from armed conflict: they are the internal effects (as a result of the burdens of internally displaced persons), the regional effects (as a result of the burden of refugee's influx) and the global effects (as a result of foreign interventionists). According to him, these three ripple effects generate unique challenges. While the internal effects constitute problem of food insecurity, loss of means livelihood, rise in displacement of people, the regional effect constitute spread of contagious diseases across border from the inflow of refugees and the global effect constitute the growth in narcotics trade across borders sponsored by foreign non-state actors. As Hentz (2004) notes that such spillover has occurred in both West Africa (from Liberia) and East Africa (from Democratic Republic of Congo).

This study adopted the State fragility theory to explain the phenomena; based on three core assumptions of stateness, these include; authority, legitimacy and capacity. Authority captures the extent to which a state possesses the ability to enact binding legislation over its population, to exercise coercive force over its sovereign territory, to provide core public goods, and to provide a stable and secure environment for its citizens and communities. The authority dimension refers to the extent to which the state holds the monopoly of violence and can secure its claim on this monopoly vis-a-vis competitors. A diminished authority reduces the state's ability to define and execute rules and protect citizens from wilful violence. By implication, authority is thus related to the degree that the state can guarantee the physical integrity of its citizens and protect them from physical threats. However, a certain degree of violent crime seems to be unavoidable in any society without necessarily calling the state's monopoly of violence into question. The true question here really is whether, and to which degree, the state faces organized challenges to its monopoly of violence from one or more parties within or outside its society. An indicator that reflects our conceptualization of authority quite well is the "monopoly of violence" indicator from the Bertelsmann transformation index (BTI). It is based on expert judgment and is supposed to measure the extent to which the state monopolizes the use of force over the entire territory (Bertelsmann sifting 2008). However, BTI data is available only for about 125 countries and only every other year since 2006.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted survey research design. Survey research design consists of the use of questionnaire and interview methods. This is to allow the researcher systematically collect data from a sample of population through the use of questionnaire for making inferences and drawing conclusions. For the purpose of this study therefore, samples were carefully selected to represent the characteristics of the population and the sample size was chosen using appropriate tools. This provides the researcher with the opportunity to generalize the findings of the study for the whole population. The population of the study refers to the stakeholders and individuals who have the basic information or rather individuals that can provide basic and necessary information on the subject matter. For this study, those that fall within the confine of the study population that is the target population include: Red Cross Society (RCS) 15, Norwegian Refugees Councils (NRC) 20, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) 25, Security Agencies 1,450, National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) 225, National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMIP) 250, National Commission for Refugees (NCFR) 163, Department of Internal Conflict, Institute for Peace and Conflict Resolution (NPCR) 187, and Internally Displaced Persons Camps in Abuja 1,140. These are targeted populations was chosen because they are major stakes and mostly related to the study. Therefore, the total population used in this research is (3,475).

A sample size is a group of items taken from the population, so that the needed information can be obtained for analysis. However, in selecting the sample size the study adopted determination formula in social sciences propounded by Taro Yamane (1967) thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

When n is the sample size, N is the population size and e is the level of precision (0.05)² thus the total population for the nine organizations are 3,475 based on the selected organizations, applying the formula above the sample size is determined as thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3475}{1 + 3475(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3475}{1 + 3475(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3475}{1 + 3475(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{3475}{8.69}$$

$$n = 399.8849252$$

Therefore, (400) is a sample size of the study. However, purposive or judgmental sampling technique used to select respondents who are knowledgeable about the subject under investigation for interview. Purposive sampling or judgmental sampling uses a deliberate effort to obtain representative sampling by including typical groups or areas in the sample (Akpa, 2011). Most times, the researcher relies on expert's judgement of what is a credible criterion for picking sample units. In purposive sampling, specific elements, which satisfy some predetermined criteria are selected. Although the criteria to be used are usually a

matter of the researcher's judgement, he exercises this judgement in relation to what constitute a representative of sample with people to the research purpose. Basically, there are two main methods of data collections which the researcher used in the study. They are primary and secondary method. The primary method of data collection involved the collection of data by the used of questionnaires, interview and field survey. For the purpose of this study questionnaires were used and distributed to the research respondents that were purposively sampled from general population of the study. Secondary method of data collection were collected from document materials like textbooks, journals of same inclination, articles related to the topic of investigations, dissertation and thesis that are relevant to the topic at stake in published and unpublished works relevant to the topic of investigation gotten from Nasarawa State University Library, National Library Abuja, internet materials. The analysis of data requires a number of closely related operations such as establishment of categories, the application of these categories to raw data through, tabulation and then drawing statistical inferences. However, the topic under discussion, descriptive and inferential statistics method was used throughout in the data analysis of both primary and secondary data obtained and it was subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 20 and e-views).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The total sample size for this study was questionnaires administered and only 355 were completed and returned by respondents. However, the chapter focused on the rate of return response of questionnaires analysis and interpretation of respondent's profile and data presentation.

Table 1: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 – 25	39	10.9
36 – 39	125	35.2
40 – 59	141	39.7
60 and Above	39	10.9
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Table 1, shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents aged. Respondents between the age ranges of 18–25 has 39(10.9%) of respondents, 36–39 has 125(35.2%), 40–59 has 141(39.7%) and 50 and above has 39(10.9%) of respondents in the study.

Table 2: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	85	23.9
Married	135	38.0
Divorced	77	21.6
Widowed	58	16.3
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Table 2, indicates the respondent's marital status, this shows that the respondents who are 'single' has 85(23.9%) of respondents, 'married' has 135(38.0%) of respondents, 'divorced' has 77(21.6%) and 'widowed' has 58(16.3%) of respondents in the study.

Table 3: Sex Distribution of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	255	71.8
Female	100	28.1
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Table 3, reveals the sex, frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents which indicates that 'male' in the study participated based on the frequency and percentage of 233(71.8%) and 'female' has 100(28.1%) of respondents in the study.

Table 4: Responses on the Role Played by the NGOs in Tackling Economic Hardship and Social Problem of IDPs Camps in Abuja

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Provision of Palliative Materials	56	15.7
Provision of Healthcare Service	66	18.5
Provision of Skills Acquisition Materials	83	23.3
Resettlement of IDPs at various Camps for Proper Care	115	32.3
None of the Above	35	9.8
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Shows that 56(15.7%) of respondents responded to 'Provision of Palliative Materials', 66(18.5%) responded to 'Provision of Healthcare Service', 83(23.3%) responded to 'Provision of Skills Acquisition materials', 115(32.3%) responded to 'Resettlement of IDPs at various camps for proper care' this has the highest numbers of respondents, and 35(9.8%) responded 'None of the above' in the study.

Table 5: Responses on the Challenges Confronting NGOs on the Management of the IDPs Camps in Abuja

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Emergence of Fake NGOs	100	28.1
Diversion of the Relief Materials	60	16.9
Raping became a Serious Challenge	121	34.0
Government Policies Towards IDPs	44	12.3
None of the Above	30	8.4
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 5, Shows that 100(28.1%) of respondents responded to 'Emergence of fake NGOs' 60(16.9%) responded to 'Diversion of the relief materials', 121(34.0%) responded to 'Raping became a serious challenge's, 44(12.3%) responded to 'Government policies towards IDPs' and 30(8.4%) responded to 'None of the above in the study'.

Table 6: Respondents Responses on the impact NGOs on women and children in IDPs Camps in Abuja

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Provision of Social Needs	119	33.5
Humanitarian support	105	29.5
Protection	63	17.7
Making Propaganda	30	8.4
None of the Above	37	10.4
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Table 6, indicates that 119(33.5%) of respondents responded to 'Provision of social needs' which score the highest number of respondents in the study. 105(29.5%) responded to 'Humanitarian support', 63(17.7%) responded to 'protection', 30(8.4%) responded to 'Making propaganda' and 37(10.4%) responded 'None of the Above' in the study.

Table 7: Responses on the Effective is the NGOs in dealing with IDPs Camps Challenges in Abuja

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Well Effective	129	36.3

Effective	58	16.3
Fairly Effective	77	21.6
Not Effective	50	14.0
None of the Above	41	11.5
Total	355	100%

Source: Field Survey September, 2025

Table 7, reveals that 129(36.3%) of respondents responded to ‘Well effective’ that NGOs are well effective to deals with IDPs Camps challenges in Abuja, 58(16.3%) responded to ‘Effective’, 77(21.6%) responded to fairly effective and 41(11.5%) responded of None of the Above in the study.

DISCUSSION

Findings from the study revealed that International Non-Governmental Organisations (INGOs) have played pivotal roles in addressing both the economic hardship and social dislocation experienced by IDPs in Abuja. Respondents indicated that INGOs provided food items, emergency shelters, health services, vocational training, and cash-transfer programs to reduce vulnerability among displaced populations. These efforts were confirmed in the works of Adewale (2022) and Eze (2020), who emphasized that INGOs bridge humanitarian gaps created by inadequate government responses. Moreover, INGOs’ livelihood programs, such as tailoring, soap-making, and small-scale agribusiness initiatives, were found to empower IDPs economically and promote a sense of self-reliance. The findings also showed that women and children constitute the most vulnerable groups in Abuja’s IDP camps and are the primary beneficiaries of INGO interventions. Organisations such as Save the Children and Plan International were identified as providing maternal health care, nutritional support, hygiene kits, and psychosocial counselling for women and children. The study found that INGOs’ interventions reduced child morbidity and improved access to basic education through temporary learning centres established within camps. However, despite these positive contributions, women and children still face multiple vulnerabilities such as sexual exploitation, early marriages, malnutrition, and limited access to formal education. According to respondents, INGOs’ protective services are hindered by cultural barriers, stigma, and the absence of a clear referral mechanism for victims of abuse.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The need to properly manage IDPs in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized in as much as improper management of the group may make the countries prone to violent conflicts and other several complexities such as epidemics. However, the management of IDPs cannot be left in the hands of any one individual or group. It appears that collaboration is the name of the game. The major points of divergence between management of IDPs in Nigeria may include the fact that government agencies are the most efficient in IDPs management in Nigeria. International response to IDPs management in Nigeria has been largely inadequate. The government of Nigeria’s, has practically handed the management of its IDPs fully to the management agencies for that purpose. This is in contradiction with principle 3(1) of the UN Guiding Principles of Internal Displacement. It suffices to add that this may account for the speedy reintegration of IDPs in the country. Tied to this is the direct contact of IDPs management with IDPs themselves rather than through the government or governmental agencies, what does not seem to obtain in Nigeria. Two basic yardsticks come into play when determining the overall success of IDPs. The first is the provision of the United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal displacement while the second is reintegration of IDPs. Apparently, management agencies in Nigeria have contravened and observed alike some of the UN Guiding Principles. Therefore, considering the success of Nigeria in management of IDPs in line with the first yardstick, it could be deduced that Nigeria is more successful for the fact that the latter has contravened more of the Guiding Principles than the former. In the

inverse, it is evident that Nigeria is more successful if we consider the second yardstick (reintegration). After all, many a scholar such as Maduka (2012) has noted that reintegration which is the final and concluding stage of IDPs management ultimately seeks to support people rebuild their livelihoods including housing, sources of income, economic, social and cultural activities as well as general standard of living. In this regard, the Nigerian government still has a lot to do. To this end, no management agency can categorically be pronounced more successful than the other in management of IDPs.

Civil societies and Non-governmental organizations are important actors in the resettlement of IDPs and to sustainable community development and peace and stability building. Even though they act as complementary institutions to national authorities, their contributions are by no means little. Non-governmental organizations help raise awareness of the important protection and assistance concerns of IDPs; support the education of local elected representatives and strengthen the role of local leaders to ensure that they can respond to the important needs of IDPs. They also ensure a ready flow of information to displaced populations about durable solutions and support IDP participation in decisions about their future; monitor and report on the implementation of peace agreements with regards to their provisions for durable solutions. The following recommendations are made to strengthen humanitarian interventions, enhance coordination, and improve the living conditions of displaced populations:

- i. International NGOs should move beyond short-term relief to design and implement sustainable livelihood programmes, including vocational training, small business grants, and agricultural empowerment schemes for IDPs. Such programmes would promote self-reliance and reduce dependency on aid. INGOs should collaborate with government agencies to integrate IDPs into existing social protection programmes such as conditional cash transfers, school feeding initiatives, and micro-credit schemes. Humanitarian interventions should be community-driven. INGOs must engage IDP leaders, youth groups, and women's associations in project planning and implementation to ensure ownership, cultural sensitivity, and effectiveness.
- ii. Since women and children constitute the most vulnerable groups among IDPs, INGOs should adopt gender-responsive humanitarian strategies. These should include maternal health services, psychosocial counselling for survivors of gender-based violence, and reproductive health education. INGOs, in partnership with the Universal Basic Education Board and UNICEF, should provide non-formal education, mobile classrooms, and scholarship schemes for displaced children in Abuja. Access to education is vital for breaking cycles of poverty and trauma among displaced families. Women in IDP camps should be supported through micro-finance initiatives, cooperatives, and entrepreneurial training. Empowered women are more likely to support the education and nutrition of their children, contributing to long-term camp stability and welfare

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